

INFORMATION ON DEVELOPING THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

Head of the Startup Ecosystem Development Department of the Innovative Development Agency under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation
Ilkhamov Azizbek Yodgorovich

Abstract: We can see that ideas and innovations, which are the product of intellectual potential, are highly valued in today's world, and we can see that great attention is paid to this direction in all countries of the world. In this article, startup projects and our young people, who are the initiators of them, are discussed.

Keywords: startup ecosystem, youth policy, video selector, youth notebook, training for modern professions.

Today, our president pays great attention to the development of the startup ecosystem.

Under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoev, a meeting of video selectors is being held on measures to increase the efficiency of work in the field of youth policy and to further improve the system of working with them.

It is known that in 2021, the practice of returning the social tax paid to enterprises employing young people under 25 years of age was introduced. More than 9,000 enterprises benefited from it, 150 billion soums of social tax were returned to them, and employment of 100,000 young people was provided. Therefore, it was decided to extend this experiment for another 2 years.

Starting from June 1, it was ordered to introduce a system of paid internships in state organizations for students who entered the "youth register".

Taking into account the growing interest among young people in areas such as IT, advertising, cinema, architecture, design, marketing, handicrafts, and

painting, regional governors were instructed to establish one "Creative Park" by the end of the year. Privileges and benefits granted to IT park residents are applied to them.

For these purposes, the "New Uzbekistan Youth Initiatives" fund and electronic platform will be established. 100 million dollars will be allocated to the fund. These funds are allocated to the best ideas, start-ups, and projects of talented young people on convenient and light terms, if necessary, without interest or collateral.[1]

At the meeting, it was also announced that the system of using the funds of the "Youth Notebook" fund will be changed.

"Although this fund should serve to train young people in more professions and entrepreneurship and ensure their employment, the governors are using only 10 percent of the funds for employment, 5 out of 25 aid provided through the "Youth Register", - the press service said.

Therefore:

- Now young people will be allowed to simultaneously use similar services, such as training for a profession, labor tools, seed-planting subsidies;
- 2.5 million soums for seeds and seedlings will be given directly for purchase from seed farms in that region;
- In working with "Yoshlar Daftar", special attention is paid to training young people in modern professions such as animation, design, logistics operator, and tour guide. 10-11th grade students of schools are also covered by this system;
- from now on, at least 40 percent of the "Youth Notebook" funds will be directed to vocational training;
- 100 billion soums will be allocated for training in modern professions this year and at least 25 thousand young people will be trained.[2]

Until now, the Agency for Innovative Development has financed 137 start-up projects with a total value of 104.0 billion soums, and as a result of the projects, more than 100 new enterprises and 1 200 About 100,000 jobs have been created. The total production volume of these factories is equal to 134.2 billion soums (about 12 million US dollars) in 1 year, and about 150 new types of services and products are offered. This year, it is planned to finance 122 more start-up projects and create more than 100 completely new enterprises. Most of these projects will be implemented in remote areas of our republic, especially in innovative districts.

In addition, in the last 5 years, to further support the startup ecosystem, 19 infrastructure facilities have been established in our country, and startup incubator centers are gradually being established in each higher education institution. In particular, 6 youth technology parks with a total value of 40.8 billion soums were established in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Andijan, Samarkand, Syrdarya, Tashkent, and Navoi regions. In the future, 7 more youth technoparks will be established in Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Fergana, Khorezm, and Surkhandarya regions.

About 50 accelerator programs, more than 500 seminars and trainings, information sessions, and international meetings were organized over the past five years at the initiative of the agency and other organizations to develop the startup ecosystem. As a result of the events, the number of applications for startup competitions increased by 15 times compared to 2018, and the financing of projects increased by 5 times.

In 2023, the Tashkent startup ecosystem was included among the Top-600 (580th place) cities of the world according to the report of Startup Blink international rating agency as a result of about 50 successful global startups.

In the financing of start-up projects, not only state grants but also preferential loans, subsidies, and loans are established. Also, the practice of venture financing is working in our country, taking into account the international experience. In

particular, 27 projects with a total value of 3 million US dollars were financed on investment terms by 4 venture capital companies.

Used literature

1. https://uza.uz/uz/posts/yoshlar-bilan-ishlash-hayot-mamot-masalasi_473811
2. <https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2023/04/11/fund>